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Effects of ginseng on the human health.

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Rakhmatov Bobur Yusupovich.**

Abstarct. Ginseng plant contains carbohydrates, vitamins, proteins, amino acids, micro and macro elements necessary for human health. Currently, promising varieties of the ginseng plant are spreading around the world. The homeland of the ginseng plant is China, and it can be found on mountain slopes, rivers, and lakes.

Introduction. In accordance with President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's decision No. PQ-4901, to create a single base of scientific research on the cultivation and processing of medicinal plants in the territories of the Republic, to study the advanced scientific developments of foreign countries, to establish cooperation with leading scientific institutions and in order to introduce modern technologies and scientific developments to the republic and to strengthen the effective use of existing opportunities:

1. Forestry on the basis of the State Committee of Forestry, the Ministry of Agriculture, the Ministry of Innovative Development, the Ministry of Health and the Center for Cultivation and Processing of Medicinal Plants of the Academy of Sciences to approve the proposal to establish a scientific-production center for the cultivation and processing of medicinal plants (hereinafter - the Center) in the form of a state institution under the state committee.

2. The following should be defined as the main tasks of the center: cultivation and processing of medicinal plants on a scientific basis, formation and implementation of a unified strategy for their rational use;

Studying and identifying the reserves of wild medicinal plants in the territory of the Republic, maintaining the gene pool of existing bioresources, establishing mother plantations; conducting scientific and practical research related to cultivation and preparation of seed materials, reproduction, organization of collective nurseries and processing of their raw materials; development of specific scientifically-based proposals for the establishment of cultural cultivation of medicinal plants, taking

into account specific soil and climate conditions; study of the chemical composition of medicinal plants, product standardization and certification; conducting marketing research to study the demand of domestic and foreign markets for medicinal plants; One of the most urgent tasks is to prepare programs and organize a training system aimed at improving the skills of managers and specialists of farms, organizations and other entities that grow and process medicinal plants.

The purpose of the study. Studying the effects of the ginseng plant on human health and growing the plant using its roots.

Ginseng tea has a wonderful effect on human health. To prepare this tea, boiling water is poured over the dried and crushed ginseng root, it is covered and left to rest for 20 minutes, and then it is passed through a cheesecloth. Drink 1 tablespoon of tea 3 times a day for 1 month, then take a 30-day break and repeat the course of treatment. Such brewed tea has general strengthening, energizing and calming properties. The active substances of the plant strengthen the activity of the nervous system, reduce physical and mental fatigue, improve the activity of the heart and blood vessels, increase appetite, regulate arterial blood pressure, and increase work capacity.

Ginseng enhances blood formation and improves memory, normalizes metabolism and cardiovascular activity. Ginseng is a plant that improves eyesight, helps heal wounds, relieves pain, and calms the nervous system. Ginseng prevents premature aging of the body. This plant strengthens immunity, helps to dissolve excess fats in the body. In folk medicine, ginseng is used as tincture, decoction, ointment, tea, and dried.

Laboratory method of research. The laboratory analysis was carried out at the Departments of Biotechnology and Livestock Products Storage and Processing Technology of the Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Livestock and Biotechnologies.

Conclusion. Cultivation of promising varieties of the ginseng plant in accordance with the soil and climate conditions of our republic, obtaining high yields and processing them for the production of tinctures and useful drinks, as well as providing quality and cheap medicines to the population.

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Блокчейн-технология в бухгалтерском учете и аудите

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Аннотация

За последнее десятилетие популярность блокчейн-технологий значительно возросла, изменив не только экономическую среду, но и определив новые подходы к управлению бизнесом. Настоящая статья посвящена инновационным направлениям в области бухгалтерского учета и аудита благодаря развитию блокчейн-технологий, поскольку данная технология может оказать влияние на целые отрасли, включая финансовый сектор. Переход к финансовой системе со значительным элементом блокчейна открывает множество возможностей для профессии бухгалтера, когда навыки аудитора будут направлены в большей мере на рассмотрение вопросов более высокого уровня.

Ключевые слова:

аудит, безопасность системы, блокчейн, бухгалтерский учет, минимизация рисков утечки данных, снижение затрат

Annotation

Over the past decade, the popularity of blockchain technologies has increased significantly, changing not only the economic environment, but also defining new approaches to business management. This article is devoted to innovative areas in the field of accounting and auditing due to the development of blockchain technologies, since this technology can have an impact on entire industries, including the financial sector. The transition to a financial system with a significant blockchain element opens up many opportunities for the accounting profession, when the auditor's skills will be directed more to the consideration of higher-level issues.

Keywords:

audit, system security, blockchain, accounting, minimization of data leakage risks, cost reduction

Цифровизация стала неотъемлемой частью современного и стремительно развивающегося мира. Цифровые технологии распространяются во всех развитых странах и странах с переходной экономикой, в том числе и в Российской Федерации. Они окружают нас везде: от повседневного общения до производственных процессов [1-6]. Несомненно, цифровизация не обошла стороной и бухгалтерский учет и аудит. Для упрощения ведения бухгалтерского учета, аудиторской деятельности создаются и внедряются все новые инструменты, основанные на применении цифровых ресурсов в работе организаций. С помощью таких ресурсов повышается производительность компаний, их конкурентоспособность, совершенствуется рабочая среда персонала организации. Кроме того, руководители организаций, особенно организаций крупного бизнеса, ставят оцифровку данных о деятельности предприятия, то есть преобразование информации в цифровую систему, одной из ключевых задач и одним из главных приоритетов. Именно поэтому исследование данного процесса в отрасли финансов является актуальным на сегодняшний момент.

Можно выделить следующие преимущества цифровых технологий:

1. Оптимизация и упрощение цифровых платформ.
2. Упрощение традиционного производства.
3. Совершенствование методов построения стратегии ведения бизнеса.
4. Выполнение трудоемких задач в более короткие сроки, нежели требовались ранее.
5. Минимизация ошибок в вычислительных расчетах. Научные работы, проводимые в сфере исследования влияния цифровых технологий на бухгалтерский учет, широко распространены. Так компания Robert Half Finance & Accounting провела опрос о роли использования блокчейна (последовательного соединения блоков записей, фиксируемого электронной подписью [8]) в ведении бухгалтерского учета. Согласно проведенному

исследованию, 36 процентов респондентов утверждают, что работники отдела бухгалтерии должны будут пройти переподготовку для адаптации к новым методам ведения бухгалтерского учета; 34 процента ответили, что это повысит необходимость в специализированном учете; 30 процентов респондентов утверждают, что отдел бухгалтерии будет вынужден больше сотрудничать с от- делом информационных технологий; 29 процентов вы- ступили за то, что использование блокчейна повлияет на бухгалтерский учет, только когда эти процессы станут регулироваться на государственном уровне. И только 9 процентов опрошенных уверены, что это никак не повлияет на финансовый учет.

Вопросам учета и аудита в условиях применения информационных технологий посвящены работы таких авторов как: Одинцов В. Палий, Д. Панков, В. Подольский, А. Романов, Т. Синглетон, Я. Соколов, Дж. Хантон, Дж. Холл, Э. Чамберс. Вопросы применения компьютеров в аудите рассматривали также Н. Абдолмохаммади, Г. Боднар, П. Уильямс, А. Уильямсон, Дж. Ван Дийк, Р. Каскарино, Дж. Робертсон, Дж. Чемплейн, В. Хопвуд и другие.

Каждый из указанных ученых внес свой вклад в развитие науки, однако вопросам роли технологии блокчейн в развитии бухгалтерского учета и аудита внимание в научной литературе практически не уделялось.

Также уделяется внимание возможности и перспективности применения технологии в банковском секторе с целью скорейшего принятия кредитными организациями решения о предоставлении услуг благодаря оперативному анализу финансовых показателей в сравнении с другими социальными и персональными данными клиентов и повышение эффективности бизнеса благодаря внедрению технологии блокчейн.

Согласно отчету Jupiter Research, внедрение блокчейна позволит банкам реализовать экономию на трансграничных расчетных операциях в размере до 27 миллиардов долларов к концу 2030 года, сократив затраты более чем на 11%. Ethereum, в частности, уже продемонстрировал разрушительную

экономику, создав более чем 10-кратные преимущества по стоимости против существующих технологий. Финансовые учреждения признают, что технология распределенных бухгалтерских книг позволит сэкономить миллиарды долларов для банков и крупных финансовых учреждений в течение следующего десятилетия [5].

По оценкам Всемирного экономического форума, к 2027 году 10% мирового ВВП будет сохраняться на базе технологии блокчейн.

Итак, возвращаясь к вопросу роли блокчейн в развитии бухгалтерского учета и аудита, следует отметить, что описанные выше тенденции и направления использования технологии требуют в первую очередь соответствующей организации учета. К вопросу аудита следует подходить с пониманием, что происхождение каждой операции возможно проверить с помощью истории предшествовавших ей операций.

Важно, что все принципы ведения бухгалтерского учета остаются неизменными с соответствующим применением элементов метода бухгалтерского учета. Изменяется только технология обработки, сохранения, передачи и накопления информации. Так, например, при операциях с активами полностью соблюдаются принципы их учета и признание: контролируемый хозяйствующим субъектом в результате прошлых событий и от использования, которого ожидают поступления будущих экономических выгод. При этом блокчейн позволяет осуществить полный, автоматизированный аудит всех операций для признания контролируемости актива организации [7]. Такая проверка реализуется посредством построения и сохранению в блоках информации о первоисточнике происхождения любого актива благодаря описанным выше механизмам сохранения информации: каждая цифровая транзакция оставляет уникальную запись в базе данных, создавая возможности для аудита любого цифрового события в прошлом. Такая запись делается во всех связанных с данным активом реестрах, и каждая организация в своей копии такого реестра может получить доступ к соответствующей информации, зная необходимый ключ. Имея доступ к

реестрам, другие заинтересованные лица могут получить полную и непредвзятую информацию об объекте исследования, например, принятие решения о выдаче кредита банком или проверки полноты уплаты налогов и тому подобное – блокчейн позволяет осуществить полный, автоматизированный аудит всех операций.

В статье мы исследовали современные подходы к определению технологии блокчейн и очертили ее роль в развитии бухгалтерского учета и аудита. Доказано, что такая распределенная база данных является технологией работы с информацией и не меняет основополагающих принципов и основ бухгалтерского учета и аудита. Выяснено, что операции, фиксируемые в такой базе данных, считаются достоверными и могут быть использованы как доказательная база при принятии решений банками о предоставлении клиентам кредитов, по судебным делам и тому подобное. Подтверждением этого является практическая реализация технологии блокчейн в учете операций в отдельных странах, в том числе, и на государственном уровне.

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Candidosis

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Abstract: Candidiasis (thrush) is a type of fungal infection caused by microscopic yeasts belonging to the genus *Candida* (primarily *Candida albicans*). All representatives of this generation are conditionally pathogenic.

Microorganisms of the genus *Candida* are part of the normal microflora of the mouth, vagina and colon of most healthy people. Candidiasis is associated not only with the presence of fungi of the *Candida* genus, but also with their proliferation and/or with the fall of more pathogenic strains of the fungus. Often, candidiasis begins with a decrease in general and local immunity.

Yeast fungi of the genus *Candida* belong to deuteromycetes - immature fungi. The most common species among patients are *Candida albicans* and *Candida tropicalis*.

The main features that distinguish *Candida* fungi from true yeasts are:

Presence of pseudomycelium;

Absence of ascospores;

Characteristic cultural features.

Most people are exposed to *Candida* in the first year of life, and according to some sources, even in utero. The possibility of infection of the fetus is confirmed by the detection of the fungus in the amniotic fluid, placenta, umbilical cord. Later, the contact of the baby with *Candida* fungi occurs during the passage of the birth canal, in contact with the breast during breastfeeding, through the skin of the hands or household items during care. can be These fungi are found in sufficient quantities in raw meat, dairy products, vegetables and fruits. The source of the fungus, in addition to carriers, can be young animals (calves, puppies, horses), as well as poultry.

The occurrence of candidiasis is a frequent side effect of the use of broad-spectrum antibiotics that are active against most gram-positive and gram-negative microorganisms.

Symptoms and signs of candidiasis

Manifestation of candidiasis depends on the location of the process. Superficial and systemic (visceral) candidiasis is distinguished.

Superficial candidoses

Superficial candidiasis includes skin, mucosal lesions, candidal onychia and paronychia.

Fermental paronychia and onychia

Paronychia is characterized by swelling, infiltration, hyperemia of the nail plates, absence of cuticle (eponychium). The side of the nail is slightly pushed to the surface of the nail. Often, paronychia and onychia are present at the same time.

Candidamicides

Candidamicides is a secondary allergic rash, which indicates significant sensitization to the pathogen and its vital products. It is polymorphic, usually in the form of erythematous-squamous swollen spots, as well as urticaria and bullous rashes. The formation of candidamikids is accompanied by subfebrile, and the increase of the main inflammatory processes in the main foci.

Candidiasis of the mucous floor of the oral cavity

This form is more common in newborns (but can be observed at any age). The mucous membrane of the cheek, as well as the part of the tongue and the throat, is covered with a liquid coating (the coating is like cottage cheese, that is, the mucous membrane is just looks like he ate cottage cheese or drank kefir). If during or before pregnancy, the mother has observed similar things in the vagina or felt unpleasant sensations (itching) in the genital area (vaginal candidiasis), it can be sure that it is candidiasis. In most cases, oral candidiasis does not cause any danger if it is treated in time and correctly. If the use of local means is ineffective, it is necessary to seriously approach the study of the nature of this process.

Intestinal candidiasis

Intestinal candidiasis is one of the types of severe dysbacteriosis. In cases where conditions are created that are unsuitable for normal microbes to live in the intestine, candida will multiply. It is characterized by diarrhea, excess gas in the intestines,

and white impurities in the stool. This form of candidiasis is dangerous for small children, they lose weight and growth, lose vitamins and other useful substances necessary for normal growth during diarrhea.

Vulvovaginitis, balanitis and balanopostitis with candidiasis

In candidiasis of the genitals, a large amount of white, curd-like secretions is released, itching is observed. For vaginal (vaginal) candidiasis, as for other forms, a disturbance in the balance of the normal microflora living in the mucous membrane is characteristic. In the treatment of genital candidiasis, it is necessary to take into account that the sexual partner should also be treated, because the infection with the fungus can be repeated.

Symptoms of candidiasis in women

Burning and itching in the external genital area;

White, curd-like discharge from the vagina;

Pain during sexual intercourse;

Pain during urination;

Pungent, unpleasant smell.

Symptoms of candidiasis in men

Itching and burning in the penis and groin area;

Redness of the head and glans;

The formation of a white crust on the head of the penis and in the groin;

Pain during sexual intercourse;

Pain during urination;

Sperm-like white discharge during urination.

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Features of the course of fibromyalgia syndrome in patients with a comorbid condition.

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Relevance. Primary fibromyalgia syndrome (PFS) is an extra-articular rheumatic disease characterized by generalized muscle pain, skeletal muscle fatigue, and decreased pain threshold on palpation at specific points.

The purpose of the study. Clarification of the role of neurotic disorders, psychological defense mechanisms, the level of subjective control and types of attitudes towards the disease in the formation of the internal picture of the disease and consideration of the features of clinical and psychological relationships in patients with fibromyalgia syndrome.

Materials and research methods. 100 patients with SPF were under observation. All patients were women, aged 21 to 54 years. The mean age was 43.85 ± 0.70 years. The average duration of the disease was 7.23 ± 0.47 years. The distribution by profession showed that the vast majority belonged to the engineering, technical and administrative staff - 76%, the non-working population amounted to 2%, and only 14% were in working professions. The control group consisted of 35 patients with insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM), matched by sex and age, and participating in a medical and educational program. To determine the severity of the pathological process, the main clinical characteristics of the disease were used (Wolfe F., 1990).

Research results. All patients complained of pain in 4 or more anatomical regions for at least 1 year. The main localization of pain was noted in the axial region (the area of the muscles of the neck and upper shoulder girdle), the muscles of the back, and also the lumbar spine. Significantly less often, the pain was localized in the areas of the hip joints and distal extremities. The pain was aggravated under the influence of stress, in a state of fatigue, after increased physical activity and the need to stay in an uncomfortable sitting position for a long time, in a period of damp, cold and windy weather. Thus, according to the results of the examination in the group of

patients with SPF, the clinical level of neurotic manifestations was noted in 62.25% of cases, averaging 6.46 ± 0.15 points for depression scales, 6.72 ± 0.17 points for asthenia, anxiety - 6.8 ± 0.98 and hypochondria - 5.53 ± 0.18 points. When analyzing the correlations between neurotic disorders and the main clinical symptoms of the disease, it was found that depression directly correlated with the intensity of the pain syndrome ($r=0.35$, $p=0.011$), sleep disturbance ($r=0.30$, $p=0.002$) and the number of diagnostic tests. pain points ($r=0.41$, $p=0.038$). Asthenia and hypochondria directly correlated with pain syndrome in patients with SPF ($r=0.40$, $p=0.030$ and $r=0.320$, $p=0.001$), fatigue ($r=0.24$, $p=0.019$ and $r=0.30$, $p=0.002$), sleep disturbance ($r=0.31$, $p=0.04$ and $r=0.26$, $p=0.009$) and the number of diagnostic pain points ($r=0.30$, $p=0.038$ and $r=0.20$, $p=0.041$). The data obtained may indicate that the severity of clinical symptoms can be considered as one of the predisposing factors in the development of neurotic disorders in patients with SPF.

Conclusions : The type of attitude to the disease in SPF depends on the severity of clinical symptoms: moderate manifestations of pain, fatigue, sleep disorders are associated with an ergopathic type of attitude to the disease; severe musculoskeletal pains are associated with neurasthenic, sensitive and egocentric types of response.

Anthrax

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Anthrax (bad-quality carbuncle, anthrax, Russian. sibirskaya yazva) is an extremely dangerous infectious disease for all types of farm and wild animals, as well as for humans. The disease passes with lightning speed, acute, acute and subacute (in sheep and cattle), acute, subacute and angina (in pigs), and in humans mainly carbunculosis will be in the form

There are also oropharyngeal and gastrointestinal forms. The disease is characterized by intoxication, the development of serous-hemorrhagic inflammation in the skin, lymph nodes and internal organs; skin or septic form (animals also have intestinal and pulmonary forms).

The causative agent of anthrax

Bacillus anthracis is a bacterium that causes anthrax

Anthrax, known since ancient times by the names "holy fire", "Persian fire" and other names, has been mentioned several times in the works of ancient and oriental writers and scientists. A detailed description of the clinic of this disease was compiled by the French doctor Moran in 1766. Before the revolution in Russia, the disease was mainly spread in Siberia, so it got the name "Sibirskaya yazva".

Anthrax bacteria form spores when there is access to oxygen outside the body, as a result of which they have a high resistance to high temperatures, dryness and disinfectants. Spores of anthrax bacteria can persist for many years; pastures contaminated with feces and urine from infected animals can harbor anthrax spores for many years. Vegetative forms of the anthrax bacillus die quickly when boiled and under the influence of ordinary disinfectants.

During autoclaving at 110 °C, spores die after forty minutes, and with dry heat at 140 °C in 2.5-3 hours. Anthrax spores can withstand direct sunlight for 10-15 days. Activated solutions of chloramine, hot formaldehyde, hydrogen peroxide also have a sporicidal effect.

EPISOOTOLOGY

As a source of infection, infected agricultural animals with a gross form of the disease serve: cattle, horses, donkeys, sheep, goats, deer, camels. Domestic animals - cats, dogs are less sensitive.

Anthrax in animals is characterized by the following features:

A short incubation period that usually does not exceed 3-4 days;

Significant clinic in the form of high fever, weakening of cardiovascular activity, meningeal events, bloody diarrhea and vomiting;

The rapid development of the infectious process usually leads to the death of animals in the first 2-3 days.

Cattle and horses with large horns: usually sharp and subsharp. Description:

Septic form: with a sharp increase in temperature, apathy, decreased productivity, swelling of the skin hanging on the head, neck and under the neck;

Intestinal form: apathy, refusal to eat, bloody diarrhea and vomiting, with tympany.

Pigs: (anginous form) occurs only in pigs and is asymptomatic; the changes are observed only in the case of characteristic catarrhal-hemorrhagic inflammation of the lymph nodes can be determined during the anitary examination.

Anthrax epizootics are geographically connected to soil foci - reservoirs of pathogens. Primary soil foci are formed in pastures, slaughterhouses, places where animal corpses are buried, and similar places when the soil is directly damaged by the excrement of diseased animals. Secondary soil foci are formed when spores spread to other places with rain, melt and wastewater.

Damage can occur with the participation of many infectious factors. They include secretions from the skin of an infected animal infected with anthrax spores, internal organs, meat and other food products, soil, water, air, and environmental objects.

Susceptibility to anthrax in humans does not depend on the age, gender and other physiological characteristics of the organism; it is related to the ways of damage and the amount of the infecting dose.

PATHOGENESIS

The gateway to anthrax infection is usually broken skin. In rare cases, the bacillus enters through the mucous membranes of the respiratory tract and the gastrointestinal tract. An anthrax carbuncle is formed where the pathogen enters the skin, in the form of a necrotic inflammation, swelling of adjacent tissues, and a serous-hemorrhagic focus with regional lymphadenitis.

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Comparative analysis of the use of various scales in the diagnosis of herniated discs.

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Relevance. Back pain affects up to 80% of the population aged 20-50 years. It is the second most common reason for visiting a doctor after respiratory illness and the third most common reason for hospitalization.

The purpose of the study . To study the possibilities of using various scales for the course of intervertebral hernia of the lumbosacral spine

Materials and research methods. The work is based on the analysis of the results of a comprehensive examination of 115 patients with neurological manifestations of lumbosacral disc herniation. Therapeutic manipulations - intervertebral disc puncture and laser exposure were performed by a neurosurgeon using local anesthesia in a sterile operating room. The clinical part of the work is based on an assessment of the dynamics of neurological disorders in patients who previously had no effect from conservative treatment and received puncture laser treatment. To do this, we used the traditional neurological examination of the patient, the collection of anamnesis upon admission to the hospital and the questioning of the patient. Neurological examination was carried out in full according to the generally accepted method. To record the data of the neurological examination, the developed examination card of the patient was used .

Research results. The average duration of exacerbation and conservative treatment before the use of PPLDD was 8.1 ± 2.5 weeks . All patients during the exacerbation before the use of puncture laser treatment received conservative inpatient 98 (85.2%) or outpatient 17 (14.8%) treatment. 115 (100.0%) patients received medical treatment, 94 (81.7%) - physiotherapy, manual therapy and massage - 84 (73.1%). All patients underwent a CT or MRI study before using PPLDD. Lesion level data: LiV - L v - 48 patients (41.5%); Lv - Si - 56 patients (48.5%), in 11 cases, disc herniations were found at two levels, therefore, a clinically significant level for

PPLDD was determined. Paramedian hernias prevailed - 80 observations (69.5%), the average size of the hernial protrusion was 7.6 ± 1.1 mm. In the neurological status of patients who had no effect from conservative treatment and were referred for treatment according to the PPLDD method, the following symptoms were noted: pain in the lumbosacral region in 107 patients ($93.6 \pm 1.9\%$), radicular pain radiating to the leg in 95 ($82.6 \pm 3.1\%$), sensory disorders in the zone of root innervation in 87 ($75.4 \pm 2.8\%$), decreased muscle strength in the leg in 82 ($71.3 \pm 4.9\%$), decreased or absence of deep reflexes in 80 ($69.6 \pm 4.1\%$), tension symptoms in 78 ($67.8 \pm 2.9\%$). Functional disorders were identified in the lumbosacral spine: limitation of mobility in 94 ($81.5 \pm 4.7\%$) patients, static disorders in the form of various variants of antalgic pose installations in 87 ($75.7 \pm 3.9\%$).

Conclusions . Thus, a decrease in hernia density by 35.4 ± 8.2 HU, a decrease in its axial size by 2 or more times can be used as an early neuroimaging criterion for the clinical effectiveness of the proposed method of treatment.

Constipation

Mo'minova Hilola

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Abstract: Constipation is a feeling of incomplete emptying of the bowel, even if a person does not have a bowel movement (defecation) for more than 48 hours.

The frequency of defecation in a healthy person depends on diet, habits and lifestyle. People suffering from constipation often complain of chronic fatigue, bad taste in the mouth, nausea, loss of appetite. Constipation sufferers have a swollen abdomen, unhealthy yellowish-brown skin, frequent use of laxatives disrupts intestinal absorption, and as a result mild anemia and vitamin deficiency can be observed.

Constipation or constipation

Constipation affects 20% of the world's population, mostly in developed countries. The problem of intestinal dysrhythmia is relevant for all age groups. Constipation often develops in people between the ages of 25 and 40, and the problem worsens later. Constipation in fertile (reproductive) age is characteristic of women. Constipation is 5 times more common in elderly people than in young people. Such recognitions are recognized by most researchers dealing with age-related gastroenterology problems.

In clinical medicine, organic and functional constipation are distinguished:

1. Organic constipation. It develops due to morphological and anatomical changes of the intestine (often diagnosed in childhood) or pathological and iatrogenic reasons (probability is almost the same in young and middle-aged people).

Organic constipation occurs as a result of the following factors:

Congenital anomalies (dolichocolon, dolichosigma, colonoptosis);

Complications of intestinal surgery;

Inflammatory (adhesion) process in the intestine and omentum;

Intussusception (intestinal penetration into the intestine), violation of the omentum, twisting of the intestine, intestinal obstruction;

Cancer tumors in the intestine or its surrounding organs crush the intestine.

2. Functional constipation. Disorders of the psycho-emotional state of a person develop in disorders of the motor, secretory, excretory and absorption functions of the mucous layer of the large intestine. Morphological changes are not detected in the intestine. Functional constipation is part of a group of pathologies combined with intestinal impaction syndrome (ITS). A syndrome is a combination of one pathogenesis and various etiological (causal) symptoms. A disease as a nosological unit is always united by common etiology and pathogenesis.

Organic constipation is associated with surgical pathologies, usually manifests itself in an acute form and develops due to congenital characteristics of the intestine. In some cases, it is necessary to eliminate defects quickly. If organic constipation occurs due to intussusception, scarring, intestinal twisting, obstruction of the intestinal cavity or foreign body, the clinical picture develops rapidly and immediate surgical intervention is required to save the patient's life. The clinical manifestations of acute constipation are very obvious and are relatively easy to detect with equipment.

Functional constipation often has different etiology and pathogenesis, is often chronic and cannot always be easily treated. Most people who suffer from functional bowel dysrhythmias do not consider themselves sick.

Clinicians divide people with STIs into two categories:

"Not a patient", has symptoms of constipation, but does not consult a doctor for various reasons. Pathology does not significantly affect their lifestyle;

Patients who feel discomfort consult a doctor. Pathology affects the quality of life in different ways.

Functional disorders of the gastrointestinal system are determined on the basis of characteristic symptoms (by rejection) using the entire spectrum of diagnostic techniques. In some cases, it is difficult to eliminate the symptoms of chronic constipation.

A set of symptoms is analyzed to diagnose functional constipation. In clinical practice, diagnostic criteria are usually refined by laboratory, instrumental, and functional diagnostic methods.

Normal defecation is a sign of a healthy person. In various sources, the norms of defecation periodicity, size, shape and consistency of daily litter mass are given.

The proper functioning of the digestive system is characterized by the following signs:

In a healthy person, bowel movement (defecation, defecation) is from 2 times a day to three times a week;

The shape of feces is cylindrical (like a sausage);

The consistency of stool is light.

Sometimes constipation is not associated with diseases and has a normal, random nature. However, any constipation is almost always a sign of gastrointestinal pathologies manifested by constipation and other symptoms.

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Typhoid fever

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Abstract: Diarrhea, typhoid fever is an acute cyclic intestinal anthroponosis infection caused by *Salmonella typhi* (*Salmonella enterica*, serotype typhi) bacteria. It is characterized by alimentary transmission, fever, development of typhus, general intoxication, roseola rash on the skin, hepato- and splenomegaly, and specific damage to the lymphatic system of the lower part of the small intestine.

One of the first historically known epidemics of typhoid fever is the Plague of Athens. In 2000, 21.6 million people in the world were diagnosed with diarrhoea, and about 1% of them died due to the disease.

The causative agent of the disease is *Salmonella enterica*, genus *Salmonella*, serovar Typhi belonging to the family Enterobacteriaceae. The first record of this bacterium was published in Zurich in 1880 by Ebert. At the same time as Ebert, Koch, Klebs and Meyer were also engaged in the study of bacteria.

In 1884, the causative agent was isolated in its pure form by Gaffka, a student of Koch, and named "Ebert-Gaffka typhoid bacillus".

The bacterium is mobile, gram-negative, has round ends, and stains well with all alinine dyes. No exotoxin. After it dies, it releases endotoxin, which is considered pathogenic only for humans. Does not form spores.

Sweating bacteria are quite stable in the external environment: they can be stored in clean water reservoirs for up to a month, in vegetables and fruits for up to 10 days, and in dairy products they can multiply and accumulate.

Under the influence of 3% solution of chloramine, 5% solution of carbolic acid, mercuric chloride (1: 1000), 96% ethyl alcohol, they die after a few minutes.

EPIDEMIOLOGY

Reservoirs and sources of the pathogen: patient or carrier (temporary, acute or chronic).

In the 1-5 weeks of the disease, the excretion of the pathogen with feces is most often observed. This indicator reaches its maximum level in the 3rd week. Urinary excretion is observed during 2-4 weeks of the disease.

Convalescents often continue to shed pathogens for 14 days (temporary carriage). This process lasts up to 3 months in 10% of those who experience the disease (acute transmission). 3-5% of them become chronic carriers and can continue to release the typhoid bacterium into the environment for several years.

The variable nature of typhoid virus shedding in chronic carriers makes it difficult to identify and increases their epidemiological risk.

The mechanism of transmission of the pathogen is fecal-oral. The main way in most cases is water, but food (kefir, sour cream, milk, yogurt, minced meat, etc.) and transmission in everyday conditions are also recorded.

Humans have a high natural susceptibility, but the clinical symptoms of the disease can vary from subtle to severe forms. After the disease is over, stable immunity remains in the body.

MAIN EPIDEMIOLOGY SIGNS

The disease has a ubiquitous distribution, but is more common in areas with poor water supply and sanitation. Teenagers and adults are often affected by water contamination, and young children are more often affected by dairy products. The disease is more common in summer and autumn.

SYMPTOMS

The incubation period lasts from 6 to 30 days, on average 2 weeks. The general chain of the course of the disease: Trigger - mouth - intestines - Peyer's plaques and solitary follicles (lymphadenitis and lymphangitis) - bloodstream - bacteremia - the first clinical manifestations.

Microorganisms circulating in the blood are partially killed and release endotoxin, which causes intoxication syndrome, and in massive endotoxemia leads to infectious-toxic shock.

The initial period (the time from the onset of fever to its permanent maintenance) lasts 4-7 days and is characterized by increasing symptoms of intoxication. Pale skin

color, weakness, headache, loss of appetite, bradycardia is observed. White coating on the tongue, constipation, flatulence, diarrhea is characteristic.

The peak period is 9-10 days. Body temperature is constantly maintained at a high level. Signs of intoxication are evident. Patients are inhibited, have a negative attitude towards others.

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Постстенотическое расширение восходящей аорты как фактор риска при протезировании аортального клапана.

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Цель. Оценка влияния постстенотического расширения восходящей аорты на результаты хирургического лечения пациентов с пороком аортального клапана.

Материал и методы. В отделении хирургии сочетанной патологии сердца ГУ «РСНМПЦХ» им. В. Вахидова с 2012 года по настоящее время выполнено 90 оперативных вмешательств на восходящей аорты в сочетании с протезированием аортального клапана. В группу исследования вошли пациенты с аортальным стенозом, которым было выполнено протезирование клапана за указанный период. Срочность и повторный характер операции, наличие значимой патологии митрального клапана, расширение восходящей аорты более 55мм были критерием исключения из исследования. Средний возраст больных составил 50.35 ± 12.78 лет. Мужчин было 50 (55%). Этиология аортального порока была представлена двустворчатым аортальным клапаном (52%), дегенеративным поражением (21,5%) и ревматизмом (26,5%). По данным ЭхоКГ: конечно-диастолический объем левого желудочка составил $112,2 \pm 27$ мл, фракция выброса $60,1 \pm 2,4\%$, градиент систолического давления (ГСД) на аортальном клапане составил $95,3 \pm 26,3$ мм.рт.ст.

Результаты. Госпитальная летальность после протезирования аортального клапана составила 4,8%. При сопутствующем аортокоронарном шунтировании летальность была 8,8%. Причинами летальных исходов были острая сердечная недостаточность, нарушения ритма сердца, дыхательная недостаточность и полиорганная недостаточность. Наличие постстенотического расширения восходящей аорты до 50 мм. При этом по возрасту и среднему значению EuroSCORE (6,3% и 6%) группа больных с дилатацией аорты не отличалась от остальных пациентов. Наличие

двустворчатого аортального клапана, а также процедура окутывания аорты статистически не были связаны с высокой смертностью и риском осложнений.

Выводы. Протезирование аортального клапана в сочетании с умеренным расширением восходящей аорты, на современном этапе характеризуется приемлемым уровнем операционного риска. Риск и сложность операции при комбинированном протезировании аортального клапана и окутывании восходящей аорты не отличаются от таковых при изолированном протезировании аортального клапана. Механизм, а также причины повышения летальности в группе больных с дилатацией аорты требуют дальнейшего исследования.

Патофизиологические механизмы у пациентов с гипопитуитаризмом

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Актуальность: Гипопитуитаризм является редким, недостаточно изученным расстройством, его предполагаемая частота составляет 4,2 случая на 100 000 в год, а предполагаемая распространенность - 45,5 случаев на 100 000 (без учета гендерных различий).

Цель: выявить патофизиологические механизмы развития заболевания гипопитуитаризмом.

Материалы и методы:

Гипопитуитаризм — это состояние здоровья, характеризующееся снижением выработки гормонов гипофизом. Патофизиология гипопитуитаризма обычно включает повреждение гипофиза, что делает его неспособным вырабатывать один или несколько гормонов нормальным образом.

Когда один или несколько гормонов гипофиза не вырабатываются, железа, на которую нацелен тропный гормон гипофиза, обладает сниженным секреторным действием. При нормальных условиях уменьшение действия железы-мишени или снижение концентрации вторичных гормонов стимулирует гипофиз вырабатывать больше гормона, чтобы усилить эффект. Это известно как отрицательная обратная связь в гомеостазе.

Однако при гипопитуитаризме гипофиз или некоторые из составляющих его секреторных клеток не способны адекватно реагировать на снижение целевых уровней гормонов. В результате действие желез-мишеней остается низким. Это в конечном итоге приводит к недостатку гормонов, вырабатываемых мишенью.

В отличие от оценки желез-мишеней, функцию гипофиза обычно оценивают путем объединения функции железы-мишени с концентрацией стимулирующего или тропного гормона гипофиза. Концентрация вторичного гормона тироксина в крови, а также концентрация тропного гормона тиреотропина или тиреотропностимулирующего гормона используются для оценки функции гипофиза в регулировании функции щитовидной железы.

Низкий уровень тироксина в сочетании с аномально низким или даже нормальным уровнем тиреотропина, таким образом, указывает на заболевание гипофиза, а не щитовидной железы. Это происходит потому, что нормальный гипофиз увеличивает выработку тропного гормона в ответ на низкую концентрацию гормонов щитовидной железы в крови.

Результаты: Гипопитуитаризм развивается после нарушения цепи гомеостаза, что приводит к остановке физиологического процесса и разрывает цепь отрицательной обратной связи. Из чего следует, что гормоны не высвобождаются из гипофиза таким же образом, как клетки-мишени.

Заключение: Патофизиологическим процессом болезни гипопитуитаризма является повреждение гипофиза и нарушения гомеостаза

Частота рака молочной железы в регионах приаралья.

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Resume. Despite the achievements of modern medicine, breast cancer remains the main cause of death. According to the data of the World Health Organization, 2.3 million cases of disease and 685,000 deaths occur worldwide every year. The incidence of breast cancer is increasing in all countries, especially in East Asia. Considering this, the aim of our research was to study the incidence of metastatic cancer among the population living in the Aral Sea region. The materials of the Khorezm branch of the Republican Scientific and Practical Oncology Center were analyzed retrospectively. In analysing was used the WHO classification for age determination. Findings of medical histories for the period 2018-2021 showed that recurrent and metastatic breast cancer in the Aral Sea region was more common in middle-aged women (48.6%), mainly in indigenous women.

Keywords: breast cancer, metastases, histological variants

Рак молочной железы (РМЖ), несмотря на выдающиеся технологические достижения современной медицины, все же остается заболеванием с очень высоким летальным риском.

По данным ВОЗ в 2020 году на рак молочной железы пришелся каждый восьмой новый случай рака в мире и каждый четвертый - среди женщин: это заболевание диагностировали у 2,3млн человек, 685 тысяч от него скончались. Заболеваемость РМЖ высока практически во всех развитых странах мира (Александрова Л.М. соавт., 2017).

Заболеваемость РМЖ растет в большинстве стран мира, особенно в странах Восточной Азии. В Китае ежегодный прирост заболеваемости РМЖ составил 5%. В то же время смертность от РМЖ во многих западных странах начала снижаться. Например, в США темп снижения составляет 1,7% в год (Williams D.R., Mohammed S.A., Shields A.E., 2016).

Цель исследования. Изучить случаи рецидивирующего рака молочной

железы в регионах приаралья (Хорезмская область).

Материалы и методы исследования. Материалом послужили постоперационные патогистологические препараты, истории болезни за 2018-2021 годы Хорезмского филиала республиканского научно-практического онкологического центра.

Результаты исследований. Ретроспективно были проанализированы материалы Хорезмского филиала республиканского научно-практического онкологического центра и в 22 случаях обнаружен рецидивирующий рак молочной железы. Проведен анализ по возрасту, национальному признаку, гистологическим вариантам, классификации TNM, имевшимся осложнениям, по сопутствующим заболеваниям и по распространенности процесса.

При анализе использована классификация ВОЗ по определению возраста и были получены следующие данные: наибольшее количество рецидивов (10 случаев) наблюдалось у женщин среднего возраста (45-59 лет) и это составило 45,4%, в молодом (18-44 г) и в пожилом возрасте (60-74 г) выявили по 6 случаев, что составило 23,3%. Все 22 женщины были представительницами коренного населения.

По гистологическим признакам на инвазивный рак пришлось 5 случаев (22,7%), внутрипротоковый – 4 (18,18%), дольковый рак - 3 (13,6 %).

По классификации TNM, по 4 случая T2T0M1, T2N1,M1 ,что составляет 36,4 % всех случаев.

По локализации процесса - поражения правой молочной железы имели место в 13 случаях, что составило 59,1%.

В 17 случаях имели место осложнения в виде анемии средней степени и 2 -х случаях болевой синдром, в 14 случаях сопутствовал гепатохолецистит и в 3 -х случаях - хронический панкреатит.

При анализе историй болезней, у 183 женщин был установлен метастазирующий рак молочной железы. По возрасту они распределились следующим образом: в молодом возрасте (18-44 г) болели 32 женщины и это составило 17,5%, в среднем возрасте (45-59 лет) – 89 (48,6 %,) в пожилом

возрасте (60-74 г) – 60 (32,8%), в старческом возрасте (74-90 лет) у 2 (1,1%).

Все 183 женщин, у которых был выявлен рак, были коренного населения. Жителей города было 42 (22,95%), села - 141 (77,05%).

При анализе стороны поражения органа у 99 (54%) женщин рак был выявлен в правой молочной железе, а у 83 (45,5%) - в левой молочной железе, у 1 женщины (0,5%), были поражены обе железы.

При анализе начала сроков заболевания большинство женщин (33) считает себя больной в течение 4 лет (18%), 28 - в течение 5 лет (15%), и 21 - течение 3 -х лет (11,5%). В большинстве случаев метастазы выявлены в легких (у 70 женщин - 38%), в печени (у 48 - 26%), в разных отделах позвоночника (у 43 - 23,5%), в различных костях тела (у 38-21%), в головном мозге (у 6 - 3,3%).

Выводы. Таким образом, ретроспективный анализ историй болезни за период 2018-2021 годы, показал, что рецидивирующий и метастатический рак молочной железы в регионе Приаралья встречался чаще у женщин среднего возраста (48,6%), только у коренного населения. Внутрипротоковый рак, как гистологический вариант, был диагностирован у 46% женщин, чаще имело место поражение правой молочной железы.

При метастатическом раке имели место отдаленные метастазы в легкие, печень и кости тела, в головной мозг.

Полученные результаты свидетельствуют о необходимости тщательного обследования женщин во время диспансеризации и профосмотров с целью ранней диагностики рака молочной железы.

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Защита миокарда при открытых операциях на сердце у детей.

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Ключевые слова: кардиopleгия, врожденные пороки сердца, детский возраст.

Цель. Защита миокарда в значительной степени способствовала значительным достижениям в детской кардиохирургии. Новые усовершенствования в методах перфузии и кардиopleгии находятся в стадии оценки. Генетические факторы также являются многообещающими инструментами для оценки и улучшения защиты миокарда.

Недавние результаты. Растет сомнение в эффективности гипотермии в предотвращении послеоперационных осложнений. Педиатрическая перфузия постепенно переходит к теплой перфузии и позволяет избежать негативных побочных эффектов гипотермии. Существует также большое количество доказательств превосходства кровяной кардиopleгии над кристаллоидной кардиopleгией. Активация белка теплового шока может быть важным фактором в улучшении защиты миокарда. Эффективность и безопасность прерывистой кардиopleгии теплой кровью были продемонстрированы в Европе в крупных исследованиях. В настоящее время проводится проверка преимуществ малого шунта и бескровной хирургии.

Заключение: Кардиopleгия является наиболее важным фактором защиты миокарда, но все аспекты процедуры должны быть связаны с защитой сердца. Появляются доказательства того, что тепловая хирургия с низким первичным шунтированием и прерывистой кардиopleгией теплой кровью является действенной альтернативой гипотермической перфузии с холодной кардиopleгией с использованием большего первичного объема.

Development of a method of management of patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease

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The aim of the study - to develop a method of management of patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease.

Material and methods. In order to carry out the research, 149 patients with CKD who underwent inpatient and later outpatient treatment in the therapy and rehabilitation department of the Central Military Hospital under the State Security Service in 2019-2021 were examined.

A total of 149 patients, including 60 (40.3) administrative staff, 43 (28.8) emergency staff, 26 (17.44) emergency security staff, 16 (16) emergency technical staff (10.73%), 4 (2.68%) of the operational-combat team were selected for this study. Their average age was 38.2 ± 6.6 years.

Subgroups B with E were combined into subgroup B because the results of the examination were similar, so that the number of patients in this subgroup B reached 47. Since different changes were observed in subgroup A and B, indicators in 2 subgroups (a-Administrative and B operational and combat content) were taken for comparison.

Results. An algorithm for diagnosing and treating the disease was compiled for military patients with NAFLD in accordance with their type of Service. According to this algorithm, if patients with obesity are diagnosed with steatosis after undergoing liver Utsis, its alternative causes are excluded, if there is no steatosis, patients are prescribed SHP+JF. Then the diagnosis of NAFLD is made and the indicators of the functional state of the liver are determined if the military working in the administration from the types of services, if increased diet №5+ursosan+ademethionin+ atorvaktor (in case of dyslipidemia) is prescribed, if the indicators are not exceeded and the military of another type of Service diet №5+physical activity is considered sufficient.

Conclusion. When ursosan and atorvastatin were used in combination with a personalized diet, including control of protein, fat and carbohydrates, in patients

with NAFLD, a significant decrease in the main parameters specific to the disease was observed compared to patients of the control group.

The dangers of being weight and sensitivity—weight-related health problems

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Abstract: Until recently, one thing was clear: excess weight is an unnecessary problem. Today, it has been found that being underweight is more dangerous than being overweight.

Both excess and deficiency of body weight pose a threat to people's health. However, according to modern ideas, especially in people over 40 years of age, average fullness is better than underweight.

Key words: weight, danger, overweight, health, thin, disease

Thinness (especially noticeable) rarely appears out of nowhere. It is usually associated with asthenia, insufficient nutrients in the diet, or undiagnosed chronic diseases. Therefore, as a rule, thin people have less vital energy than fat people, who are not called strong people for nothing.

It should be remembered that an important indicator of the body's well-being is not only correct, but also stable weight. Constant changes in weight have a negative effect on both health and general condition.

Dangers of underweight

1. Mental weakness

Researchers say that underweight people between the ages of 50 and 60 are more likely to develop dementia than their normal-weight peers. The reasons for this are not yet clear.

2. Sterility

In the absence of adipose tissue, sex hormones are not synthesized, and in turn, the lack of these hormones "turns off" the reproductive function: in men, the production of spermatozoa is weakened, and in women, the menstrual cycle either stops or is disrupted, and egg cell maturation process is broken. Women with adipose tissue deficiency have a 72% increased risk of miscarriage.

3. Problems related to psychology

Underweight individuals are prone to depression and mood swings. The reason for this is lack of nutrients in the diet and hormonal imbalance. Depression patients, for example, have an average of 25% lower folic acid levels than normal people. Lack of mood is also caused by a lack of carbohydrates in the diet, because carbohydrates stimulate the production of substances responsible for good mood (serotonin and tryptophan).

4. Osteoporosis

Underweight usually means low bone density, which in turn leads to osteoporosis.

5. Decrease of immunity

Lack of nutrients also leads to decreased immunity and anemia. The lack of iron and B vitamins, which are responsible for the production of erythrocytes (red blood cells), is especially dangerous. Such a patient often catches colds, feels cold all the time, gets tired quickly (iron deficiency leads to chronic fatigue) and is nervous out of nowhere.

Dangers of excess weight

1. Cancer

Overweight, especially obesity, 12 types of cancer (esophageal, thyroid, stomach, liver, kidney, brain, pancreas, breast, gall bladder, endometrial, ovarian and colon cancer) increases the risk of development. Scientists say that excess weight disrupts the hormonal background and metabolism, which leads to mutations in cells.

2. Diabetes

Accumulation of fat leads to impaired carbohydrate metabolism and insulin sensitivity, which in turn leads to the development of diabetes. According to doctors, the risk of disease increases when the weight is 20% extra.

3. Joint diseases

Excess weight accelerates damage to ankles and joints. For example, each additional kilogram increases the load on the knee joint by about 4 kg. As a result, arthritis, arthrosis, osteoarthritis develops.

4. Infarcts, stroke

Excess weight causes an additional load on the work of the heart and "tires" it faster. More than 70 percent of obese people are diagnosed with atherosclerosis and 40 percent with hypertension. Infarcts are 5 times more common in obese people than in thin people.

5. Apnoea

The main cause of sleep apnea is the accumulation of fat around the neck, which narrows the airways while lying down. Apnea causes chronic insomnia that activates the sympathetic nervous system. As a result, the number of heart contractions increases, blood pressure rises, and heart rhythm disorders occur.

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Clinical and functional analysis of the treatment of children with peripheral nerve diseases.

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Annotation. Late detection spasticity reduces the effectiveness of rehabilitation measures in general, adversely affecting the functional outcome.

The purpose of the study. Explore Opportunities multimodal approach in the diagnosis and treatment of spasticity of the lower limb in the early recovery period of polyneuropathies in children.

Materials and research methods. A total of 70 children with various lesions of peripheral nerves took part in the study. The duration of participation in the study for the full sample of patients ($n = 70$) was 3 months. Four examinations were carried out (on days 1, 14, 30 and 90 of the study), including a clinical neurological assessment and clinical and functional testing (according to the modified Ashworth , Tardieu , FIM, Rankine , Barthel scales , determination of the Rivermead mobility index , measurement by visual -analogue scale, assessment of the degree of movement disorders according to the scale of the Scientific Center of Neurology of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences).

Research results. All patients were assessed using the Modified Ashworth Scale (MSE), which is the gold standard for assessing muscle tone. The groups were homogeneous in terms of the distribution of baseline ISE scores ($p = 0.2316$; Fisher's exact test). At the first examination in both groups, only values of 2 or more points according to the ISE were recorded: 2 points in 21 (60.0%) patients in group 1 and in 15 (42.9%) patients in the comparison group; 3 points in 14 (40.0%) patients in group 1 and 20 (57.1%) in the comparison group.

The regression of pathological muscle tone in the comparison group was more intense, and already from the second examination, patients in this group had

statistically significantly lower scores compared to the comparison group ($p < 0.0001$ at each of examinations 2, 3 and 4; exact test Fisher).

decrease to 1 point according to the ISE in the comparison group after three months of the study (examination 4) was achieved by 20 (57.1%) patients, to 1+ point — 9 (25.7%) patients; in 6 (17.1%) patients, by the time of the last examination, 2 points remained, however, an improvement of at least 1 point was noted in all patients of group 1. At the same time, in the group of muscle relaxants 1 and 1+ points after three months were observed only in one (2.9%) and five (14.3%) patients, respectively; 21 (60.0%) patients in the comparison group retained their original ISE score (10 - 2 points, 11 - 3 points).

Conclusions: As a result of a comprehensive clinical assessment of patients in the early recovery period after lesions of peripheral nerves, it was revealed that spasticity is a factor that reduces the volume of active movements in the ankle joint, reduces the rate of recovery, the ability to move independently, social and household activity, preventing the achievement of individual rehabilitation goals .

Clinical and functional status of patients with lesions of the peripheral nervous system.

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Annotation. Recent years are characterized by an increase in the representation of motor disorders in the general structure of lesions of the nervous system in childhood. One of the most common causes of severe damage to the motor system in children is polyneuritis.

Purpose of the study. To assess the possibility of early diagnosis of spasticity in children with diseases of the peripheral nervous system.

Materials and research methods. Under observation were 109 children with diseases of peripheral nerves (89 with polyneuritis and 20 with plexalgia of various etiologies) aged 3 to 16 years, 50 girls and 59 boys, who made up the first group consisted of 22 children (11 boys and 11 girls) with HMSN type I; mean age - 12.3 ± 4.2 years.

Clinical research methods included the study of anamnesis, assessment of neurological, orthopedic, somatic statuses, ophthalmological, speech therapy, psychological and other special examinations. Standard laboratory, neuroimaging (CT and MRI) and neurophysiological examinations accepted in a neurological clinic (ECHO- encephalography, EEG, etc.) were carried out.

Instrumental research methods included MRI-study and neurophysiological techniques - TMS and ENMG. MRI was performed on tomographs " Broker Tomikon " or " Pinker ". In all cases, the brain and, if indicated, the spinal cord was examined.

Research results. When conducting CT and MRI studies in children with PNS diseases, the following changes were found: 1) expansion of the ventricular system and subarachnoid spaces, as a rule, asymmetric - 49.5%; 2) local changes in the form of hemispheric cysts - 15.6%; 3) change in the density of the medulla in the

periventricular region - 71.6%; 4) anomalies in the development of the brain in the form of micro- and pachygyria, hypoplasia and flattening of the corpus callosum, anomalies of Arnold - Chiari and Dandy-Walker, vascular malformations - 21.1%. When conducting TMS in patients with PNS diseases, the most striking changes were a decrease in the amplitude of the HME, a change in its shape, and, sometimes, an increase in its duration (Fig. 1). An increase in VCMP was also found, which was especially significant in children with PNS diseases. VCMP in the study of leg muscles exceeded the normative data by more than 3 standard deviations in 67% of patients in almost all age groups, which indicates a violation of the cortico -spinal pathway.

Conclusions: Registration of the ipsilateral response in patients with PNS diseases (in 58.3% in children with polyneuritis and in 70% with plexitis) is combined with the presence of severe paresis and the appearance of plus-symptoms in the neurological status in the form of mirror movements in the unaffected limb and/or synergistic friendly movements on the side of hemiparesis.

Features of the state of the lipid profile and cardiovascular system in obese adolescents.

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Annotation. The results of own studies of 80 adolescents with overweight and exogenous constitutional obesity of the first degree are presented, the relationship of the initial structural and geometric changes of the myocardium with lipid metabolism disorders is shown.

Keywords: adolescents, obesity, dyslipidemia, cardiovascular system.

The purpose of the study. To study the features of the state of the lipid spectrum and the cardiovascular system in adolescents with exogenous constitutional obesity of the first degree.

Materials and methods of research. A comprehensive clinical examination of 80 adolescents aged 15 to 18 years (46 girls and 34 boys) with exogenous constitutional obesity of the first degree and 30 adolescents with normal weight, who made up the control group, was conducted. The examination included an assessment of anamnesis, anthropometry data, metabolic parameters (high-density lipoproteins, low-density lipoproteins, cholesterol, triglycerides, atherogenicity coefficient), as well as a targeted examination of the cardiovascular system: electrocardiography, doppler echocardiography, cardiointervalography).

Results. It was found that overweight was observed from the first years of life in 30% of children, from 7-8 years – in 50%, from 11-12 years – in 20%. The analysis of complaints revealed that headaches in 50%, heart pain and shortness of breath during physical exertion in 40%, palpitations at rest were presented by 20% of boys and 30% of girls, cases of increased blood pressure during physical and psychoemotional loads up to 130 ± 10 and 90 ± 10 mm.rt.st. - in 18% of the surveyed. Adolescents had abdominal type of obesity (80%), body mass index 31.74 ± 0.73 kg/m², OT/OB 0.88 ± 0.02 , striar syndrome (55% of patients), vegetative disorders -

acrocyanosis, marbling of the skin, hyperhidrosis of the palms and feet (80% of patients), muffled heart tones (45%).

The laboratory study revealed the proatherogenic nature of changes in the serum lipidogram, in particular, in adolescents with exogenous constitutional obesity of the first degree, the average serum lipoproteins were within optimal values, but the levels of high-density lipoproteins were lower (0.98 ± 0.02), and low-density lipoproteins were higher (3.22 ± 0.17), according to in relation to the control indicators (1.21 ± 0.08 and 2.39 ± 0.32 , respectively). During the examination of the CCC: an electrocardiogram recorded sinus rhythm (50% of children), sinus arrhythmia (30% of patients), moderate sinus tachycardia (20%). Violation of intraventricular conduction (10% of subjects), violation of repolarization processes (75%).

Echocardiography revealed: MARS - abnormal chords in the left ventricle (60% of children), grade I mitral valve prolapse with grade I regurgitation (20%), open oval window (6% of patients), thinning of the atrial septum in the area of the oval fossa without disruption of communication (3%), the following corresponded to the upper limit of the norm indicators: end-diastolic size of the left ventricle (30% of children), thickness of the posterior wall of the left ventricle and interventricular septum (70% of the examined). The stroke volume of blood was increased (30%), the cavities of the left ventricle and left atrium were expanded (45%). The study of vegetative homeostasis in overweight children by cardio intervalography showed its heterogeneity with a predominance of parasympathetic activity of the autonomic nervous system (66%). With minimal physical exertion, excessive activation of the sympathetic part of the autonomic nervous system was noted. Vegetative reactivity had a multidirectional character: hypersympathicotonic when moving to an upright position in 54%, normotonic variant was noted in 36% of children, asymptotic type in 10% of the subjects.

Conclusions. The proatherogenic nature of changes in the serum lipidogram, as well as initial structural and geometric changes in the myocardium, hypersympathicotonic variant of the functioning of the cardiovascular system in

adolescents with exogenous constitutional obesity of the first degree can be considered as triggers for the development of cardiovascular complications.

Комплексная оценка комбинированной терапии больных с акне.

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Республиканский специализированный научно-практический медицинский центр дерматологии, венерологии и косметологии МЗ РУз. Угри являются результатом комбинированного действия бактерий и воспалительных факторов в сальной железе волосяного фолликула. При нормальных обстоятельствах кожа может противостоять влиянию внешних факторов в том, что многие микробы колонизируют поверхность кожи, обеспечивая защитный барьер для кожи.

Цель исследования. Обосновать с клинической точки зрения необходимость применения комбинированной формы терапии больных с вульгарными угрями.

Материалы и методы исследования. В основное исследование было отобрано 60 пациентов со средней степенью тяжести вульгарных угрей. Исследование являлось проспективным сравнительным с оценкой терапевтического эффекта в двух группах сравнения по 30 больных каждая. Первая группа пациентов, получающих антимикробных пептидов, содержащие GDP-20 для наружного применения два раза в день на пораженную кожу после умывания и системный изотретиноин (Роаккутан) в фиксированной низкой дозе 0,1–0,2 мг / кг / день; вторая группа пациентов, получающих монотерапию изотретиноином в тех же дозах с наружными индифферентными средствами в течение 16 недель.

Результаты исследования. Показаны высокая терапевтическая эффективность препарата при акне легкой и средней степени тяжести и высокая комплаентность проводимой терапии. Хороший и удовлетворительный эффект наблюдался у всех больных с легкой (12 человек, 100%) и у 21 (84%) со средней степенью тяжести акне. Отсутствие эффекта отмечено у 4 (16%) пациентов с акне средней степени тяжести и у 1 — с акне тяжелой степени. Большинство пациентов отметили достаточно быстрый и выраженный противовоспалительный эффект препарата: 23,6% оценили его как «очень хороший», 57,8% — как «хороший», 18,6% — как «средний».

Оценок эффекта в категориях «плохой» и «очень плохой» не было. Состояние интерлейкина 6 до лечения составлял $65 \pm 0,5$ пг/мл, а после лечения в основной группе составлял $10 \pm 0,3$ пг/мл. В контрольной группе состояние интерлейкина 6 было равно $44 \pm 0,7$ пг/мл. В то время как состояние интерлейкина 8 до лечения составлял $109 \pm 1,4$ пг/мл, а после лечения в основной группе составлял $72 \pm 0,8$ пг/мл. В контрольной группе содержание интерлейкина 8 после лечения составлял $96 \pm 1,2$ пг/мл.

Выводы. Таким образом, применение комплексного лечения на основе метритионина и хлорамадион ацетата приводит к улучшению как клинических, так и лабораторных показателей, что подтверждается проведенным методом лечения.

Клинико-неврологические, генеалогические и параклинические особенности микроцефалии различного генеза.

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Цель исследования: выявить клинико-неврологические и параклинические особенности микроцефалии различного генеза. **Материал и методы:** исследовательская работа основана на проспективном и ретроспективном наблюдении 67 пациентов с диагнозом «МКБ-10 код Q02; Микроцефалия». Пациенты обратились в отделение медико-генетического консультирования Республиканского и Ферганского центра «Скрининг матери и ребенка» за период 2018-2022гг. Диагноз устанавливался на основании генеалогического, клинико-неврологического и параклинических (МРТ головного мозга, ЭЭГ) методов исследования. По этиологическим факторам больные были распределены на две группы: в основную группу (23 больных из 9-и семей) составили больные дети с истинной наследственной семейной микроцефалией, вторую группу (44 больных) составляли больные с эмбриопатической и синдромологической микроцефалией. Возраст больных варьировал от 3 мес. до 14 лет. **Результаты:** родителей больных основной группы состояли в родственном браке во втором и третьем поколениях; При вторичной микроцефалии в анамнезе у больных отмечалась внутриутробная инфекция, тяжелая перинатальная и интранатальная асфиксия, имелись хромосомные aberrации. У больных группы сравнения клинические симптомы, особенно изменения со стороны черепно-мозговой иннервации, двигательной и когнитивной сферы были более выраженными, по сравнению с основной группой, по многим показателям выявлены значимые отличия. На МРТ головного мозга у больных первой группы отмечалось недоразвитие полушарий головного мозга (макро- и микрогирия (7,2%), гипоплазия мозолистого тела (4%), гетеротопия (2,3%)). Особенно уменьшены лобные и височные части мозга, общий вид извилин уплощен, отсутствуют третичные

извилины и борозды. У больных второй группы МРТ головного мозга морфологически отличается: помимо уменьшения массы отмечаются наличие очагов деструкции (25%), следы воспаления (15,9%), очаги кровоизлияний (20,4%), множественные кисты головного мозга (43,1%), перивентрикулярные лейкомаляции (63,6%), поражение базальных ядер (6,9%), агенезия мозолистого тела (47,2%). **Заключение:** на основании проведенного исследования выявлены различия клинического течения истинных и вторичных микроцефалий. Для верификации диагноза микроцефалии различного генеза, необходимо также пройти карио типирования и хромосомного матричного анализа, для выявления спектр структурных изменений хромосом.

О социально обусловленной природе оценки в семантической структуре слова

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Аннотация. В настоящей статье рассматриваются проблемы взаимоотношения оценки и нормы, субъективности выбора нормы, раскрывается роль контекста и ситуации общения в процессе оценивания, влияние особенностей мировосприятия личности говорящего, его ценностных ориентиров и речевого поведения.

Ключевые слова: семантика слова, оценка, норма, семантическая структура, социальный компонент, социальный параметр.

Abstract. This article discusses the problems of the relationship between assessment and norms, the subjectivity of the choice of norms, reveals the role of the context and the situation of communication in the evaluation process, the influence of the characteristics of the worldview of the speaker's personality, his value orientations and speech behavior.

Key words: word semantics, evaluation, norm, semantic structure, social component, social parameter.

Семантическая структура слова является многогранной, многослойной. Одним из компонентов структуры значения слова выступает оценочная составляющая, которая по своей природе выступает как «способ установления значимости чего-либо для действующего и познающего субъекта» [<https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Оценка>].

Процесс оценивания производится по определенной шкале:

- хорошо/плохо;
- важно/неважно;
- можно/нельзя;
- стоит/не стоит;
- дорого/дешево;
- оправданно/неоправданно и т.п.

Оценки делятся на две категории:

- 1) абсолютные оценки;
- 2) сравнительные оценки.

Абсолютные оценки. Абсолютная оценка всегда категорична: «В логике абсолютных оценок принимается, что позитивно ценное (хорошее, добро) и негативно ценное (плохое, зло) взаимно определимы: объект является хорошим, когда его отсутствие негативно ценно; объект является плохим, когда его отсутствие позитивно ценно. Напр.: «Быть здоровым хорошо, только если быть больным плохо»; «Плохо, что случаются пожары, только если хорошо, когда их нет». Безразлично то, что не является ни хорошим, ни плохим» [Ивин, Никифоров, 1997].

Сравнительные оценки. Любая сравнительная оценка производится на основе сравнения объекта оценки с другим объектом по какому-либо параметру или свойству, в результате которого субъект оценки отдает предпочтение чему-либо или кому-либо, опираясь на понятия *хуже*, *лучше*, *идентично (равноценно)*.

Категория оценки неразрывно связана с категорией нормы. Так, как отмечается в «Словаре логики» А.А. Ивина и А.Л. Никифорова, «нормы – это частный случай оценок, а именно групповые оценки, поддержанные угрозой наказания. Нормативные понятия «обязательно», «разрешено» определимы в терминах абсолютных оценочных понятий: «Обязательно А» равносильно «А позитивно ценно, и хорошо, что уклонение от А ведет к наказанию». Нормативное высказывание является сокращенной формулировкой оценочного высказывания» [Ивин, Никифоров, 1997].

Вместе с тем несмотря на то, что в основе процесса оценивания лежит сопоставление сравниваемых объектов со шкалой нормативности, сама оценка не лишена некоторой степени субъективности, которая, по мнению Н.М. Аникиной, определяется субъективностью выбора норм: «Проблема соотношения объективного и субъективного в языковой оценке в целом решается в пользу субъективности ... Во-первых, оценка есть результат отношения «субъект-человек – объект» (и в таком виде оценка вносится в план

содержания языковой единицы), во-вторых, каждый речевой оценочный акт есть действие субъекта речи. Однако, «снятая субъективность», т.е. внесенная в семантику лексемы становится объективно существующим компонентом семантики, общим для всех коммуникантов и должна определяться как социальная семантика» [Аникина, 2009, с. 14].

Социальная обусловленность природы оценки в семантической структуре слова, таким образом, проявляется в тесной взаимосвязи оценки с нормой, которая сама по себе уже является социальным продуктом.

Оценка есть признание ценности чего-либо. Ценность также является социальной категорией: «Оценка есть один из способов актуализации ценности в действительности. Она невозможна вне субъекта, так как представляет собой проявление той ценностной предметности, которая стала предметом оценки. Вместе с тем оценка несет информацию об этой ценностной предметности, т.е. отражает специфические стороны общественного бытия» [Сутужко, 2004].

Понять социальную обусловленность природы оценки помогает изучение функционального аспекта оценки, которая необходима для определения потребностей общества, которое вынуждено постоянно решать вопрос «о предпочтениях одних предметов перед другими. Именно в оценке ценностная предметность объекта находит свое актуальное выражение, становясь предметом актуальной потребности. Ценность не тождественна ценностной предметности, она является отраженной ценностной предметностью, отраженным функциональным состоянием объекта» [Сутужко, 2004].

Таким образом, оценка имеет социально обусловленный характер. Социальная природа оценки определяется необходимостью при решении вопросов о предпочтениях одних предметов перед другими оперировать категорией нормы, которая также устанавливается обществом в целях регулирования тех или иных явлений или процессов в социальной среде.

Отражая в себе внеязыковую действительность, связанную с жизнедеятельностью носителей языка как представителей определенной социальной группы, реализующих конкретные социальные роли и отношения, социальная семантика, которая репрезентируется в языке на уровне семантики, имеет важное значение в процессе взаимодействия между людьми, установления и поддержания контакта, поскольку зона социального охватывает трудовые, профессиональные, национальные, межличностные аспекты жизнедеятельности человека и социума, ролевые взаимоотношения людей.

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Фундаментальная теория современной космологии

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Теория Большого Взрыва – это не просто фундаментальная теория современной космологии, данную теорию можно рассматривать также и с позиций сотворения «Нашей материи».

Остановимся подробнее на анализе теории Большого Взрыва и проблем, связанных с данной теорией.

По современным представлениям, наблюдаемая нами сейчас Вселенная возникла $13,73 \pm 0,12$ млрд. лет назад из некоторого начального «сингулярного» состояния и с тех пор непрерывно расширяется и охлаждается. Согласно известным ограничениям по применимости современных физических теорий, наиболее ранним моментом, допускающим описание, считается момент Планковской эпохи с температурой примерно 1032 К (Планковская температура) и плотностью около 1093 г /см³ (Планковская плотность). Ранняя Вселенная представляла собой высокооднородную и изотропную среду с необычайно высокой плотностью энергии, температурой и давлением. В результате расширения и охлаждения во Вселенной произошли фазовые переходы, аналогичные конденсации жидкости из газа, но применительно к элементарным частицам. Приблизительно через 10^{-35} секунд после наступления Планковской эпохи (Планковское время – 10^{-43} секунд после Большого Взрыва, в это время гравитационное взаимодействие отделилось от остальных фундаментальных взаимодействий) фазовый переход вызвал экспоненциальное расширение Вселенной. Данный период получил название космической инфляции. После окончания этого периода строительный материал Вселенной представлял собой кварк-глюонную плазму. По прошествии времени температура упала до значений, при которых стал возможен следующий фазовый переход,

называемый бариогенезом. На этом этапе кварки и глюоны объединились в барионы, такие как протоны и нейтроны. При этом одновременно происходило асимметричное образование как материи, которая превалировала, так и антиматерии, которые взаимно аннигилировали, превращаясь в излучение.

Дальнейшее падение температуры привело к следующему фазовому переходу—образованию физических сил и элементарных частиц в их современной форме. После чего наступила эпоха нуклеосинтеза, при которой протоны, объединяясь с нейтронами, образовали ядра дейтерия, гелия-4 и ещё нескольких лёгких изотопов. После дальнейшего падения температуры и расширения Вселенной наступил следующий переходный момент, при котором гравитация стала доминирующей силой. Через 380 тыс. лет после Большого Взрыва температура снизилась настолько, что стало возможным существование атомов водорода (до этого процессы ионизации и рекомбинации протонов с электронами находились в равновесии). После эры рекомбинации материя стала прозрачной для излучения, которое, свободно распространяясь в пространстве, дошло до нас в виде реликтового излучения. Дальнейшая эволюция Вселенной по этой теории предполагает два альтернативных сценария: Вселенная либо будет бесконечно расширяться, остывать и замерзать, либо снова сожмется в точку, после чего разорвется в Большом Взрыве. Основной проблемой теории Большого Взрыва является представление о некоей сингулярности (первоначальном состоянии Вселенной, уместающейся в точку, диаметр которой близок к нулю). Кроме того, теория не дает объяснений того, что было до Большого Взрыва. С другой стороны, теория Большого Взрыва удовлетворяет представлениям о суперобъединении полей и возможности их объединении в состоянии сингулярности. Основная идея Большого Взрыва по праву принадлежит математику и геофизику А. Фридману (1922), который нашёл нестационарные решения гравитационного уравнения Эйнштейна и предсказал расширение Вселенной (нестационарная космологическая модель, известная как решение Фридмана). Фридман

заклучил, что в самом начале вся материя Вселенной была сосредоточена в компактной области, из которой и начался ее разлёт. Поскольку во Вселенной очень часто происходят процессы взрывного характера, то у Фридмана возникло предположение, что и в самом начале её развития также лежит взрывной процесс – Большой Взрыв. Дальнейшие открытия расширения Вселенной и обнаружения реликтового излучения подтверждали идею Фридмана. Как известно, теория Большого Взрыва строится на следующих положениях:

1. Сингулярность как начало зарождения Вселенной и основа физических полей.
2. Наблюдение эффекта разбегания (удаления) галактик.
3. Обнаружение реликтового излучения.
4. Низкое содержание тяжелых элементов в старых звездах.

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The lower and upper bounds of a tridiagonal 4×4 operator matrix

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Abstract. In this note a tridiagonal 4×4 self-adjoint operator matrix \mathcal{A} is considered. The estimates for the lower and upper bounds of \mathcal{A} are established. The result are applied to Hamiltonians, associated with a system describing four particles in interaction, without conservation of the number of particles on a lattice.

Keywords: tridiagonal operator matrix, Hamiltonian, lower and upper bounds, lattice, Fock space.

Let $\mathcal{H}_i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ be complex Hilbert spaces, $\mathcal{H} := \mathcal{H}_1 \oplus \mathcal{H}_2 \oplus \mathcal{H}_3 \oplus \mathcal{H}_4$. With respect to this decomposition, every operator $\mathcal{A} \in L(\mathcal{H})$ has an 4×4 operator matrix representation

$$\mathcal{A} = \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{13} & A_{14} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{23} & A_{24} \\ A_{31} & A_{32} & A_{33} & A_{34} \\ A_{41} & A_{42} & A_{43} & A_{44} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

with entries $A_{ij} \in L(\mathcal{H}_j, \mathcal{H}_i), i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4$. It is easy to check that \mathcal{A} is a self-adjoint operator if and only if $A_{ij}^* = A_{ji}$ for all $i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4$, that is,

$$\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}^* \Leftrightarrow A_{ij}^* = A_{ji}, i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4.$$

In this note we consider the operator matrix (1) in the special case where $A_{ij} = 0$ if $|i - j| \neq 1$ and $A_{ij}^* = A_{ji}$ if $|i - j| = 1$ for $i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

The main result of the present note is the following theorem.

Theorem 1. The lower and upper bounds of \mathcal{A} satisfy the estimates

$$\min\sigma(\mathcal{A}) \geq -\sqrt{\|A_{12}\|^2 + \|A_{23}\|^2 + \|A_{34}\|^2}; \quad (2)$$

$$\max\sigma(\mathcal{A}) \leq \sqrt{\|A_{12}\|^2 + \|A_{23}\|^2 + \|A_{34}\|^2}. \quad (3)$$

Example. Let $a \geq 0$, and consider the 4×4 matrix

$$M := \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & a & 0 \\ 0 & a & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Gershgorin's row sum theorem for matrices (see [2]) yields the lower and upper bounds

$$\min\sigma(M) \geq \min\{-1, -1 - |a|, -1 - |a|, -1\} = -1 - |a|;$$

$$\max\sigma(M) \leq \max\{1, 1 + |a|, 1 + |a|, 1\} = 1 + |a|.$$

By Theorem 1 we obtain $\min\sigma(M) \geq -\sqrt{2 + a^2}$, $\max\sigma(M) \leq \sqrt{2 + a^2}$.

Application of Theorem 1. Let us consider a 4×4 operator matrix in the four-particle cut subspace of the Fock space and using Theorem 1 estimate its bounds.

Let us introduce some notations. Let \mathbb{C} be the field of complex numbers, $(\mathbb{T}^d)^n$ be the Cartesian n th power of \mathbb{T}^d and $L_2((\mathbb{T}^d)^n)$ be the Hilbert space of square-integrable (complex) functions defined on $(\mathbb{T}^d)^n$ for $n = 1, 2, 3$.

Denote

$$\mathcal{H}_1 := \mathbb{C}, \mathcal{H}_n = L_2((\mathbb{T}^d)^{n-1}), n = 2, 3, 4, \mathcal{H} := \mathcal{H}_1 \oplus \mathcal{H}_2 \oplus \mathcal{H}_3 \oplus \mathcal{H}_4.$$

The Hilbert space \mathcal{H} is called *four-particle cut subspace* of Fock space.

Let A_{ij} be annihilation (creation) operators [3] defined in the Fock space for $i < j$ ($i > j$). We consider the case, where the number of annihilations and creations of the particles of the considering system equal to 1. It means that $A_{ij} \equiv 0$ for all $|i - j| > 1$. To use Theorem 1 we also assume that $A_{ii} = 0$ for $n = 1, 2, 3, 4$. In this case a operator matrix \mathcal{A} is associated to a system describing four particles in interaction, without conservation of the number of particles and acts in the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . We assume that

$$A_{12}f_2 = \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v_1(t)f_2(t)dt, \quad f_2 \in \mathcal{H}_2;$$

$$(A_{23}f_3)(x) = \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v_2(t)f_3(x, t)dt, \quad f_3 \in \mathcal{H}_3;$$

$$(A_{34}f_4)(x, y) = \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v_3(t)f_4(x, y, t)dt, \quad f_4 \in \mathcal{H}_4.$$

Here $v_n(\cdot)$, $n = 1, 2, 3$ are real-valued continuous functions on \mathbb{T}^d .

Direct calculations show that

$$(A_{12}^*f_1)(x) = v_1(x)f_1, \quad f_1 \in \mathcal{H}_1;$$

$$(A_{23}^*f_2)(x, y) = v_2(y)f_2(x), \quad f_2 \in \mathcal{H}_2;$$

$$(A_{34}^* f_3)(x, y, z) = v_3(z) f_3(x, y), \quad f_3 \in \mathcal{H}_3.$$

Under these assumptions the operator matrix \mathcal{A} is bounded and self-adjoint in \mathcal{H} .

Applying (2) and (3) we have

$$\min\sigma(\mathcal{A}) \geq -\sqrt{\|v_1\|^2 + \|v_2\|^2 + \|v_3\|^2};$$

$$\max\sigma(\mathcal{A}) \leq \sqrt{\|v_1\|^2 + \|v_2\|^2 + \|v_3\|^2}.$$

In particular, if $d = 1$ and $v_1(x) = v_2(x) = v_3(x) = \sin x$, then

$$\min\sigma(\mathcal{A}) \geq -\sqrt{3\pi}, \quad \max\sigma(\mathcal{A}) \leq \sqrt{3\pi}.$$

We remark that in [4] the cubic numerical range is used to establish new estimates for the spectrum of tridiagonal 3×3 self-adjoint operator matrices. This new bounds are compared with the classical perturbation theory as well as to the Gershgorin bounds and an application to three-channel Hamiltonians from quantum mechanics is given.

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Artificial intelligence in the development of service-oriented software

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It is increasingly acknowledged that e-governance is crucial for implementing government services. The ultimate goal of e-governance is to enable the government to deliver services to its citizens and decision-makers efficiently and cost-effectively. E-Government services have the potential to benefit both governments and citizens by increasing access to services while decreasing the cost of providing them. Over a period of time, there has been a significant advancement in technology. Governments are facing many challenges in rendering e-Government services to their citizens. To ensure that the benefits reach the last person in society, the government must promote e-Government services. Therefore, governments must apprehend the main barriers to achieving comprehensive government transformation while developing and delivering e-government services using artificial intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT) to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the benefits. For this, a reference model is required which is independent of technical platforms and organizational structure, which comprehends the framework and guidelines to deploy e-government services, analyze the services, and ease use for the citizens. The Internet is the backbone of any e-Governance services. Worldwide, efforts are being made to make e-Government services available to their citizens to reduce costs and provide efficient and effective systems. E-Governance offers new means of communication between the government and its citizens. If not correctly integrated, E-Government services may lead to various threats and will tend to fail. The breach in data privacy and security are some of the threats associated with it. Artificial intelligence (AI) techniques can provide more sophisticated solutions to these threats by detecting anomalies and securing the data to prevent threats. The Internet of things (IoT) can offer an unprecedented improvement and can significantly help in walks of our lives, and so is with the e-Government services. It can help in the surveillance and monitoring of the areas' critical security and safety,

controlling traffic management, environmental pollution, fire detection, e-Health, e-Agriculture, e-Bill payment, etc. The proposed paper will use Artificial Intelligence (AI) driven Internet of Things (IoT) techniques to analyze and enhance e-government services to all stakeholders. Also, such AI techniques will support mitigating the associated risk of cyber-attacks. Factors affecting the adoption of e-government services, design, development, and implementation initiatives based on the proposed reference framework will undoubtedly benefit all stakeholders¹

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a model in which connecting items with various sensors and actuating devices over the Internet allows for collecting, sharing, and analyzing data to enable creative applications. IoT can assist the creation of numerous new services for people, corporations, and governments by allowing interaction with a wide range of things such as household items, CCTV, smartwatches, cellphones, corporate sensors, and automobiles. This framework is used in various disciplines, including transport, electricity and utility, education medical, equipment, public security, and defense

In response to fast digital technology development, smart, innovative governance has been imagined as an evolution of e-government to invent ways for the government to achieve better citizen participation, transparency, and connectivity [3]. The development of the name “smart government” the government’s attempts to match with dynamic and ambiguous situations and achieve resiliency via the use of intelligent technology, which operates as enablers of creativity, durability, economy, and life ability. Thus, the advent of smart governments is inextricably tied to using smart (AI) systems that depend on massive amounts of data, which is frequently accessible via IoT

¹ Al-Besher, A., & Kumar, K. (2022). Use of artificial intelligence to enhance e-government services. *Measurement: Sensors*, 24, 100484. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2022.100484>

**Aspects of teaching the idioms denoting emotional condition
to B1 and B2 students**

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Abstract

This article offers some suggestions (including sample exercises) for the teaching of idiomatic language. First, the relation between non-idiomatic and erroneous language in foreign language learning is examined, and it is concluded that non-idiomatic sentences do not so much break categorical rules as venture into the grey area of weak combinatorial probabilities between linguistic items. The purpose of the study is to understand idioms and how to learn correctly with some teaching methods in English. Teaching idioms might seem intimidating, especially if your students have never come across with them before. Teaching your students with idioms early can help them communicate more naturally and give them deeper understanding of the English language. On the internet news state that there are about 25 000 idiomatic expressions in the English language, however we try to avoid using them in our recent days. Even idioms and phrases are not related to the formal language nevertheless it is the accurate way of speech in our community.

Key Words: Bartlett called this essential characteristic of human cognitive processing "effort after meaning", English in the underlying conceptual metaphors it employs and where it differs, Often B1 idioms will help students to arrive at the solution.

Introduction

This has important pedagogical implications. Bartlett F .C established in a whole series of experiments in which subjects were presented with incomplete or inconclusive drawings or narratives that subjects sought to impose meaning on the item by fitting it into their own meaning structures. Thus, stories which contained references to unfamiliar cultural practices were modified in memory so as to fit in

with subjects own cultural expectations. Bartlett called this essential characteristic of human cognitive processing "effort after meaning". The very fact that idiomatic language and proverbs are so semantically opaque makes them excellently suited to a problem-solving approach in teaching which can exploit learners innate cognitive drive to make sense out of their environment. Idioms, phrases, metaphors are regarded as the sociocultural aspects of the language which need to be focused on in teaching target (Cakir2011). English is rich with idioms. If we choose not to teach them with idioms, they will be missing an important cultural element of the language they strive to speak fluently. On the other hand, Chuang (2013) argues that the meaning of the idiom cannot be determined through individual analysis of each word which makes mastering idioms difficult. Thus, the nature of the idioms problems for language learners since their meaning are unpredictable. And, this is the main issue for the (ESL) learners which are facing in oral system of the language. In this case, teachers should know the right way of educating methods, which have to consume their students with proper idioms and phrases using in this century. Without using the idioms in English, we may lose the importance of the language.

Lennon (1998) describes idioms as the colorful side of languages. That are used to enhance the language by using the existing vocabulary items, combining them in new sentences and making new meanings and functions. It means that idioms are vital in foreign language learners to make their communication more effective in the language. With particular vocabularies that for idioms and phrases, students can use new idioms in their speech, if only they have good understanding a new word.

Significance and struggling to learn idioms among the students

Acquiring knowledge about idioms not only enables language learners to communicate well, but also enables them to learn the culture and community of the target language (Samani & Hashemian). So, every student who try to find natural way of interfacing with English, they have to find right resources filled with new words and idiomatic expressions. The recent studies shows that students have a big problem with learning idioms and the one reason is the difference between the meaning and writing form of the idioms. Also, in lots of international testing systems

idioms are not preferred to use while taking the exams of writing, because of using them incorrectly or using them too much. By having such problems, students try to avert them. After that, their understanding about the language and other skills may fall.

Native speaker uses idioms more than someone who is new to the language, because they are more familiar with them and know the context in which they should be used. So, if you use an idiom in your speech, you sound more natural to the native speaker. This can help you feel more comfortable and confident when you speak them to the contest.

Methods of teaching the idioms denoting emotional condition.

Teaching the idioms can be funny and efficient if you know relatable methods. And also, idioms are acceptable for intermediate and advanced level students, as you can imagine, it can be a little confusing if your student's level is lower than them. One method is to teach idioms in context to show them how actually be used in conversation with a native speaker. As a teacher you have to find quickly a good resource or a conversation which idioms are used. For example:

-Ann: Hi Ellen How are you?

-Ellen: Hi, I'm feeling under the weather.

And now you can see how it works naturally in context. So, for this method you have to know how to find a good context to work with idioms. Second method is to teach idioms in spoken form rather than written. The reason is that the idioms are much more commonly used in conversation rather than formal writing. Third method is teaching with pictures, and this works really fast that your student realizes idioms after watching them, it is your option to choose the picture based on your topic. Fourth method is teaching idioms slowly and based to the category. Do not force your student to learn a lot in one time after that, it will be easy to forget them. With teaching them slowly and classify them to the categories you can create easy atmosphere to learn. The last method is trying teaching them with games. One example game is drawing a picture of idiom and guessing them with letters.

Conclusion

These methods aimed to help students with their learning and also for teachers to increase their methods of teaching idioms. And these five methods can help to learn and use idioms in your speech. It also helps you if you think of English as it is your own language, you don't have to start to teach your students with most complex idioms, either – even simple “to feel under the weather” can help to connect in a more meaningful way during the conversation you are participating.

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2. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2018/09/10-reasons-why-finlands-education-system-is-the-best-in-the-world>
3. <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Link>

**Improvement of technologies of integrative approach to advanced foreign
experiences in higher education organizations**

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Annotation: The article deals with the analysis of modern educational system in comparison with educational organizations as well as education sector that is undergoing modern changes globally. The article describes that some parts of the education system are being modified, methods of educational and educational work are being modernized, and new forms of links between education systems and the labor market are being improved.

Key Words: higher educational system, professional competence, globalization, modern education, schools, universities.

Teaching is a way of human existence. The main task of modern education has become “the production of competent people who would be able to apply their knowledge in changing conditions, and whose main competence would be the ability to engage in constant self-learning throughout their lives” [1]. Professional competence is professional personal qualities and ability to act; knowledge, skills and abilities; motivation for professional activity at a high level. In the following we will analyze some factors affecting the development of the education system:

1) The level of development of social production and improvement of its scientific and technical foundations, causing ever-increasing requirements for the general educational and technical training of the bulk of manufacturers and the corresponding development of educational institutions. For this reason, in the more technologically advanced countries the network of various schools expands fast and new types of educational institutions are created earlier. At present, under the influence of scientific and technological progress in all countries of the world, a general education is actually mass, providing secondary education, a network of universities is developing, as well as vocational educational institutions.

2) State policy in the field of education, influencing the development of various types of educational institutions and the nature of their work. Sometimes it is politics that determines the existence of various types of general education schools, some of which are intended for mass education, others for serving the wealthy part of society. In England, for example, there are four types of secondary schools: public schools, grammar schools, technical schools, and the so-called modern secondary schools. The first two types of schools are intended mainly for the elite, the modern secondary school for the lower strata of society. Politics also determines the existence in individual countries, along with state secular schools, of confessional schools, and so on.

3) Pedagogical factors, such as, for example, the early education of children and the creation of preschool educational institutions for this purpose; the expediency of developing special educational institutions providing vocational training. The impact of these factors on the formation and development of education in individual countries affects differently. But gradually some general trends emerged in this respect [4].

A modern teacher should speak at least three languages: their native language, a foreign language, and the language of technology. Basic principles of pedagogical activity in interactive learning: the role of the facilitator and moderator; preliminary preparation (playing field, working groups, terms of reference, routes); subject-subject relations (student activity); self-assessment, mutual assessment, feedback. Modern teaching principles: partnership with the student, activation of the student's professional experience, interactive forms in teaching the material, minimum external control – maximum self-control of the students, the role of the teacher – facilitator (accompaniment and counseling). In modern conditions, the main thing in teaching is the passive role of the teacher and the active student.

Case technology began to be used at Harvard Business School in 1908. An ordinary student works through 500 cases per year. The case method is based on simulation or a specific example. The case used in the classroom must meet the following requirements: provide an opportunity for interpretation from the point of

view of the participants; contain problems and conflicts; be monitored and solved taking into account the individual knowledge, skills and abilities of students and allow for various solutions [2]. Cases are structured, unstructured and pioneering. Decision-making ladder: situation diagnostics, problematization, collection of alternatives and their evaluation, decision making.

Interactive technologies in the structure of seminars, the functions of the seminar in the technology of game learning: the development and consolidation of independent work skills, the ability to think professionally, manage a team, make a decision and organize its implementation. Contents: a system of educational problems and sub-problems, designing student activities, learning tasks that model professional activities. Result: development of professional knowledge and skills. Game design and project method is an independent creative work of a student, carried out from an idea to its implementation with the help of consultations with a tutor (teacher), supervisor.

A modern specialist should be educated, moral, mobile, responsible, distinguished by the ability to cooperate, creativity, use an integrative approach in activities. Integration is one of the significant innovative phenomena in education. As Karimov: "it surpasses all other phenomena" in terms of the breadth of experimental implementation, the depth of creative intent, the duration and dialectic of historical development" [3, p. 26]. Research by O.B. Akimova, I.A. Zimnyaya, E.V. Zemtsova, V.M. Lopatkina, B.Zh. Muhammadiev, Chapaeva, N.O. Yakovleva are devoted to the integrative approach. An integrative approach is a research position, according to which education is considered as a process and result of pedagogical integration (interdisciplinary, intradisciplinary, interpersonal, intrapersonal) [3, p. 44–45]. Scientists state that the integrative approach in pedagogy in different ways. I.A. Zimnyaya, E.V. Zemtsova define an integrative approach as "a holistic representation of a set of objects, phenomena, processes, united by the commonality of at least one of the characteristics, as a result of which its new quality is created" [3, p. 17]. However, on the other hand, according to Lopatkin, he believes that the integrative approach is a means that ensures "the

integrity of the picture of the world; contributes to the development of human abilities for systemic thinking in solving theoretical and practical problems” [3, p. 162]. Akimova and Chapaev argue that the integrative approach is carried out at the technological and content level. An integrative approach contributes to the solution of the following tasks: reveals the intellectual potential of the student; students' personalities; forms professional competencies; creates psychological and pedagogical conditions for self-education, self-education, self-development, socialization. Socialization is “a multifaceted process covering all spheres of an individual's life; social category with a specific result” [8, p. 86], and the given result is personal value orientations”. The main principles of the integrative approach in the study of pedagogical disciplines are: the principle of subjectivity, cultural conformity, creativity, orientation to civil-patriotic values and value relations, synergy, self-education, dialogue of cultures, variability in the choice of means of interaction between the subjects of the educational process, dialogue, feedback. The components of an integrative approach can be: organizational-methodical, activity-practical and theoretical-content. The organizational and methodological component involves the integration of teaching methods (debate, project method, moderation, deliberation, business games, discussions, round tables, festivals, competitions, conferences, case technologies). The activity-practical component includes the integration of learning forms, which will facilitate the use of creative tasks that contribute to the development of critical thinking and creativity, the formation of personally significant and professional qualities of the individual. The resource-content component integrates the resources necessary for educational and cognitive activities (classroom and extracurricular), determines the content of an integrative special course, which, due to its content, means, methods and techniques, will contribute to the formation of professional competence. Among the main goals of an integrative approach in the study of academic disciplines, it seems important to us to single out the following: the formation of civic consciousness, self-awareness of the personality of the teacher, social and legal, civil-patriotic and moral norms, knowledge; development of research, design, communication, reflective and other

skills; education of personally significant and professional qualities of a person, and others.

The implementation of this approach involves the implementation of integrative processes at four main levels of integration: interdisciplinary, intradisciplinary, interpersonal, intrapersonal. An integrative approach is based on interdisciplinary connections. The use of knowledge of an interdisciplinary nature contributes to the integration of education, the harmonization of human relations with nature through the development of a modern scientific picture of the world. It is important that students can use knowledge in a complex way, critically evaluate the phenomena being studied. In order to do this, teachers need to use innovative methods and techniques, as well as select thematic material that has educational value. As the study showed, teachers open up new opportunities for implementing interdisciplinary connections, integrating knowledge in different subjects in the minds of students; conduct interdisciplinary classes (interdisciplinary, binary, integrated).

At present, we can see that education sector is undergoing modern changes globally that some parts of the education system are being modified, methods of educational and educational work are being modernized, and new forms of links between education systems and the labor market are being improved. A thorough, systematic and objective study of international experience in the development of education has become extremely relevant. Currently, education is going through a turning point in its development, which is due to global development trends and the potential for internal changes accumulated by the beginning of the 21st century. This practice-oriented manual is an overview of the education systems of a number of foreign countries: industrialized – Australia, Belgium, Great Britain, Germany, Italy, Canada, the Netherlands, Norway, USA, France, Sweden, Japan; with economies in transition - Azerbaijan, Belarus, Brazil, Egypt, India, Kazakhstan, China, Korea, Lithuania, Malaysia, Mexico, Poland; as well as an analysis of education reforms in some post-socialist countries: Bulgaria, Hungary, Mongolia, Romania, and the Czech Republic. A review of their experience and national characteristics gives an

idea of how the main directions of development of education systems within the framework of various organizational and legal models, as well as about the specifics of the implementation of the concept of lifelong learning, the purpose of which is to build a society based on knowledge, a society where conditions are created for the education of all categories of citizens, and responsibility for learning is distributed between the state, employers, employees and citizens in general. Such a society, unlike the traditional one, is characterized as a learning society [5, p. 6-7].

Thus, outcome of the application of an integrative approach in the study of pedagogical disciplines are as in the following: optimization of the educational process; systematization of educational and cognitive activity; formation of key competencies. An integrative approach ultimately can lead to the education of qualities of a citizen's personality. Therefore, we assume that the integration can be one of the promising methodological directions of the new education system.

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